

The Effect of Corporate Governance Principles on Job Satisfaction: Research on the Asset Management Sector

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Abstract

Corporate governance defines the structure defined by the performance monitoring and evaluation system, which defines the company's objectives and the means to achieve them. Corporate governance principles, on the other hand, are defined as principles that assist corporate governance, which plays a role in policy, in assessing and improving its performance from legal, regulatory, and institutional perspectives to ensure economic efficiency, sustained growth, and continued financial stability. These principles play a crucial role in achieving broader economic objectives, such as investor confidence, capital increase, and allocation. High-quality CG creates trust, enabling capital providers to create value under unbiased and favorable conditions, while minimizing the cost of accessing capital for growth. A well-implemented CG protects the rights of not only shareholders but also other stakeholders. In this respect, CGP are important in globalizing capital markets. The objective of the research is to demonstrate the impact of CGP on JS. The survey revealed a positive relationship between CGP and JS.

Key words: Corporate Governance, Job Satisfaction, Employees, Capital Markets Board's Corporate Governance Principles, Legal Regulations of Corporate Governance

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1. Introduction

Management exists to benefit larger industries and economic sectors outside of personal stakeholders. For corporate management to be successful, it eliminates the problems that may exist during purchasing, financial reporting, identifying the

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manager and compensation. In addition, CG encompasses the relationships between a business board of directors, shareholders and other stakeholders. Designs a performance tracking and valuation system, in which the organization's goals and options for achieving them are explained.

The main purpose of human resources and workforce management is to improve the employee's attitude towards work. JS has been an important area of research for many years, and many researchers are investigating the relationship between JS and the factors affecting it.

In this study, the effect of CGP on JS was investigated. The study consists of four parts. In the first part of the study, the concept of CGP, SPK CGP and legal regulations regarding CG are discussed. In the second part of the study, subjects such as the concept of JS, the factors affecting JS, the theories about JS and the results of job dissatisfaction are tried to be explained. In the last part of the study, the effect of CGP on JS in the asset management sector was investigated and the results of the research were given.

2. Corporate Governance Principles

CGP are basically based on the principles of justice (equality), transparency (public disclosure), responsibility and accountability. Below is detailed information about them.

Transparency Policy

One of the elements of CG is transparency. Transparency ensures that CG is more effective and robust. When there is little or no transparency in companies, it becomes difficult for shareholders, other stakeholders and market participants to follow up and hold the board of directors and senior management accountable. For this reason, the aim of the transparency principle in CG includes the information necessary for the parties to evaluate the effectiveness of the board of directors and top management in business management. (Basel Committee on Banking Supervision, 2015).

The principle of transparency also means that institutions should share honest, clear, and comparable information about their financial situations, governance structures, and relationships with partners with the public in a timely manner. In short, it involves disclosing both financial and non-financial data that is not commercially confidential to the public in an open-ended and cost-effective way (İnceöz, 2026).

Equality Principle

This principle describes the protection of all shareholder rights, including minority shareholders and foreign shareholders, and the equal treatment of all beneficiaries in the management of the company. According to the principle of

equality; The CG framework should protect shareholder rights and facilitate the enjoyment of these rights. At the same time, according to this principle, all shareholders should retain the opportunity to receive compensation in case of violation of their rights (Darman et al., 2019).

The principle of fairness means treating all business stakeholders equally and protecting their rights. In short, it means taking measures to prevent others from accessing information unnecessarily and to avoid any conflicts (Özcan, 2026).

Accountability Policy

Accountability is to provide the basis of CG by constantly following the best practices and fulfilling responsibilities effectively. The driving forces of this principle are acceptance of responsibility, making ethical decisions, transparency and making clear statements, which results in a working relationship of trust and mutual benefit between the business and its shareholders. It should ensure accountability and responsible decision making throughout the enterprise with CG. In addition, CG should be responsible for the decisions, actions and performances of all participants. (Rezaee, 2007).

The principle of accountability essentially means that board members are obligated to provide explanations to the legal entities of corporations and to stakeholders (Kantarıcı and Erol, 2026).

Principle Of Responsibility

The responsibilities of corporate managers are not limited to financial reporting, performing the basic duties of doing business and complying with the laws in the law. Institutions are obliged to respond to the demands of the democratic societies in which they serve – these expectations are not stated in official law. The concept of corporate responsibility includes the tasks done for businesses to improve the mutual relationship between companies and societies. They want the demands of society to be met to carry the values of the enterprises to the top. According to experience, this enables companies to perform well. However, this is difficult for businesses in global economies. In addition to the benefits of globalization, there are such situations that cause concern for multinational enterprises. The reason for this is the fact that multinational companies are not doing enough to contribute to local economies. In addition, he is accused of taking sides in issues such as corruption of public personnel, violation of human rights and labor rights, and failure to protect the environment (Witherell, 2002). Businesses are obliged to eliminate such concerns. Otherwise, they will be damaged and suffer serious losses.

Businesses have recently taken responsibility for improving their performance in various aspects of business ethics as well as complying with the law. They follow the rules by developing various codes of conduct and management

systems. They have done it with the support of labor unions, non-governmental organizations and governments. In this respect, OECD Guidelines for Multinational Enterprises are of great importance. These principles are recommendations through governments to businesses operating in or in associated countries. These principles are the only multilaterally approved instrument for corporate responsibility and include non-OECD countries as well as business and civil society. In addition, the principles encompass all areas related to standards of responsible conduct, thus providing businesses with the most valuable international measure of society's aspirations (Witherell, 2002).

The principle that board members' decisions and the resulting actions must comply with and be monitored against company regulations, guidelines, rules, and laws is defined as the principle of accountability (Avcı, 2022).

3. Capital Markets Board (Cmb) Corporate Governance Principles

The CGP, issued by the Capital Markets Board (CMB), was published in 2003. As of this date, although it is obligatory for companies whose shares are traded on the ISE to implement the principles, some studies have been carried out by the CMB in order to encourage the implementation of the principles. At the forefront of these studies are the necessity of defining the formats of the reports on compliance with CGP and preparing the relevant reports, and the creation of a separate index based on the level of compliance with CGP in the ISE. In this way, the CMB wanted to encourage the benefits of good CG practices to be provided to companies and capital markets as soon as possible (SPK, 2022). The CGP of the Capital Markets Board consists of four main sections: shareholders, public disclosure and transparency, stakeholders and the board of directors, and their sub-headings. The main sections are listed as follows: Shareholders Principle, Public Disclosure and Transparency Principle, Stakeholders Principle, Board of Directors Principle (Kurumsal Yonetim Tebliği, 2014).

4. Legal Regulations Regarding Corporate Governance

The bankruptcy of WorldCom in the summer of 2002, followed by the Parmalat scandal that erupted in Enron and Italy, made the value of good CG felt all over the world and revealed its necessity (Darman et al., 2019). Due to the collapse of Enron and WorldCom and other corporate scandals, the USA implemented the Sarbanes-Oxley law on July 25, 2002, which is considered one of the harshest laws in its history. Every firm registered with the U.S. Securities and Exchange Commission is included in that law. The successive emergence of corruption in firms has necessitated close surveillance of audit companies and accountants (Darman, 2008).

The financial scandal of the late 90s and early 2000s, combined with the economic downturn, created problems for investors to trust. Institutional and

accounting-related scandals still cause concern for investors today. The Sarbanes-Oxley Act (SOX) and SEC-related rules emerged to restore public and investor confidence in the US (Rezaee, 2007).

While all these developments were taking place at an ordinary pace in the USA, successive studies were carried out in Europe by both the EU Commission and EU countries. While CG practices in the USA were put into action with very high-sanctioned laws such as SOX, the principle of "Apply, if not, explain" prevailed in the European Union. The first CG practices in Europe were seen in England and Cadbury Report in 1992, Combined Code, Higgs Report and Smith Report were approved in 2003. In the UK, the CG code was revised and accepted by the Financial Reporting Council in 2014 (Darman et al., 2019). The New Code consists of five main titles. These titles are Leadership, Effectiveness, Accountability, Remuneration, Relations with Shareholders. (Finansal Raportlama Konseyi, 2014).

Serious steps have been taken towards CG practices in different EU countries and codes have been adopted. Among them: Cromme Commission Code (2001) and German CG Code (2007) in Germany, Bouton Report (2003), Recommendations sur le gouvernement d'entreprise (2004), AFEP-MEDEF CG Code (2008) in Germany is located. In 2003, an action plan titled "Modernizing Company Law and Improving CG Practices" was approved by the European Union Commission. Then, in 2005, the European CG Forum was established, and successive activities were carried out. In the following years, especially after the 2008-2009 financial crises, the CG structures of financial institutions were seriously examined, and the European Union published a green book on this subject in 2010. Following the green paper, much stricter CG practices were approved for financial companies within the framework of the Capital Requirements Regulation and Directive (CRD IV package) in 2011 (Darman et al., 2019).

Although publicly traded companies operating outside the financial field did not have a significant impact on the emergence of the financial crisis, a weakness was observed in the CG practices of these companies. Thereupon, the European Union published another green book on the CG framework in 2011. The "Company Law and CG Action Plan", the final version of which was approved in December 2012, offers several initiatives to modernize the labor law framework in Europe, to play a more active role for shareholders and to sustain companies. Three main issues were examined in the said new action plan: Increasing transparency, encouraging shareholders to take more part in CG practices, supporting companies to grow and gain competitive advantage (Darman et al., 2019).

5. Job Satisfaction Concept and Dimensions of Job Satisfaction

Job Satisfaction Concept

The most common explanation for JS is Locke (1976), who describes it as "...a satisfying or positive emotional state resulting from one's evaluation of one's job or work experiences".

Research on JS began in the 1930s. Attitude measurement was also affected due to the economic and employment problems of the economic crisis (for example, the studies of Thurstone and Likert in particular). While economics is a major reason for measuring workforce morale, even if not carefully monitored, attitudinal research has gained a new perspective.

In 1955, Brayfield and Crockett conducted and published research on satisfaction and performance. Although the later studies showed optimistic results on the relationship between satisfaction and performance, it was determined that the concept needed to be developed theoretically in the late 1950s, with the idea that the development of JS could be understood more clearly and that more than one way that the workforce could provide benefits to organizational effectiveness could be clearly predicted in terms of satisfaction levels. The 1960s turned into experiments in which psychologists measured the connections of satisfaction and developed theoretical ideas. For this reason, these years have been accepted as the "golden age" in satisfaction research. In 1959, Herzberg, Mausner, and Snyderman introduced the "two-factor" theory in more than a decade of research and practice. Other important theoretical ideas of the period,

In addition, two measurement systems have emerged: the Job Descriptive Index (Smith et al., 1969) and the MSQ-Minnesota Satisfaction Questionnaire (Lofquist and Dawis, 1969). In the 1970s, there were developments in the theoretical sense. Salancik and Pfeffer (1977, 1978), social information processing theory, which states the importance of the social context of satisfaction judgments, and Hackman and Oldham's (1975) job characteristics theory, which states the importance of the characteristics of the jobs in which people work. The basis of Social Information Processing Theory is that the social environment has both direct and indirect effects on work-related judgments.

Edwin A. Locke's Affective Interval Theory (1976) is the most well-known JS model. The main premise of the theory is that JS determines the difference between what an individual wants to have at work and what he actually has. In addition, the theory measures how much importance the individual attaches to a job, and the degree of satisfaction of the individual when the demands are met. Until the 1990s, there was no theoretical development. After the 1990s, it started to be measured again through psychology (Weiss & Merlo, 2015).

Dimensions of Job Satisfaction

The factors that reveal JS are basically divided into two, intrinsic and extrinsic JS factors. (Bektas, 2017). More detailed information on internal and external JS is presented below.

Internal Job Satisfaction

Herzberg et al. (1959) focused on the differences in internal and external factors in the organization in their theory of JS. Intrinsic factors are related to the employee's demand for self-actualization at work or generally to intrinsic JS. Intrinsic JS consists of internal factors arising from work experience. Intrinsic JS is summarized as factors such as responsibility, self-direction, skill development, and a sense of accomplishment at work (Herzberg et al., 1959). Kalleberg (1977) stated in his research that IS has a great effect on JS (Kalleberg, 1977). Decker (1985) and Randolph, (2005), in their study among nurses and rehabilitation professionals, explained internal JS as a better supporter of JS than external job factors (Decker, 1985; Randolph, 2005).

Factors related to the individual include their personality, emotional state, basic needs, ideas, and demands, as well as the degree to which these elements are strong. A person's mental and physical condition, their sense of security, and the priority these demands hold for the individual all contribute to the characteristics of intrinsic job satisfaction (Yazır, 2026).

External Job Satisfaction

External factors are defined as the factors that explain company policies, supervision, satisfaction arising from wages, and external rewards and reward system accordingly (Decker et al., 2009). Willingness and skill alone are not sufficient for JS. These factors must be supported by environmental factors. The reason for this is that some elements that individuals need are met from the external environment. Inner satisfaction decreases when external tools are scarce or absent. ES refers to the employee's adaptation to the job under the influence of external factors. It has to do with goals such as winning rewards, avoiding punishment, and career advancement. When the person is willing to do a job, they want to get material and moral gains from the job (Galia, 2008).

Working conditions within an organization encompass employee relations, communication with managers, supervision, organizational policies, and the organization's relationships with its environment. Responding to subordinates' requests, fair wages for employees, occupational health and safety, and a climate of fear are all important aspects of the work environment (Yakut, 2025).

3. Research

In this section, the scope and purpose of the research, the details of the methods used in the research, demographic analysis, reliability analysis, confirmatory factor analysis, structural equation models, correlation, regression analyzes are included, and statistical analyzes of the findings are included.

Scope of Research

The aim of this study is to reveal the effect of CGP on JS. In this context, 305 institution employees operating in the asset sector were included in the research.

Research Method and Scales Used

In this study, a questionnaire technique was used to collect data. The survey consists of 3 parts. At the beginning of the survey, the participants were informed about the purpose of the study, and they were informed that there were no questions to reveal their personal information and that the data would only be used for scientific studies.

The survey consists of 3 parts and 35 questions. The first part (9 questions) includes the items affecting the employees of the institution under the title of stakeholders (employees) under the CGP of the CMB. CGP used in the study, Assist. Assoc. Dr. Abdullah Fatih Akcan from the master's thesis titled "The Effect of Adoption of CGP on Organizational Attractiveness and JS" written by Alper Emrah Coşkun under the consultancy of Abdullah Fatih Akcan in 2017. Minnesota JS Scale Used in the Study. Instructor It is taken from the master's thesis titled "The Effect of Employees' Perceptions of Organizational Power and Organizational Justice on JS " written by Selçuk Şimşek in 2021 under the consultancy of Leyla İçerli. There are two sub-dimensions, IS and ES in the scale, which includes a total of 20 statements. In the last part, there are 6 demographic questions.

Demographic Analysis

Table 1. Socio-Demographical Distribution of Participants

	Personal Characteristics	n	%
Age	18-25 years	270	88,5
	26-33 years	16	5,2
	34-41 years	19	6,2
	Total	305	100,0
Gender	Woman	174	57,0
	Male	131	43,0

	Total	305	100,0
Marital status	Single	124	40,7
	Married	181	59,3
	Total	305	100,0
Educational Status	High school and below	26	8,5
	Licence	216	70,8
	Degree	58	19,0
	Doctorate	5	1,6
	Total	305	100,0
Institution Working Time	Less than 1 year	47	15,4
	1-5 years	155	50,8
	6-10 years	69	22,6
	Over 10 years	34	11,1
	Total	305	100,0
Institutional Position	Starting Position	70	23,0
	Mid-Level	95	31,1
	Manager		
	Expert Position	101	33,1
	Senior Manager	39	12,8
	Total	305	100,0

Looking at Table 1, it was seen that 88.5% of the contributors to the study were between the ages of 18-25, and 6.2% were between the ages of 34-41. 57% are female and 43% male. While 59.3% of them are married, 70.8% have a bachelor's degree and 1.6% have a doctorate degree. While 50.8% of them have 1-5 years of experience, 33.1% of them work in an institution as a specialist.

Reliability analysis

Table 2. Reliability Analysis Findings

Scales	Cronbach's Alpha	Number of Items
Corporate Governance Principles	,943	9
Job Satisfaction	,959	20
Internal Satisfaction	,939	12
External Satisfaction	,902	8

The Cronbach Alpha value of the CGP scale, which is one of the scales used in the study, was determined as 0.94. The Cronbach Alpha value of the JS scale, which is another scale used in the study, is 0.959. The Cronbach Alpha value of the

sub-dimensions of the JS scale was determined as 0.939 for IS and 0.902 for ES. The scales are highly reliable and suitable for use in analysis.

Confirmatory Factor Analysis (Dfa)

Table 3. Compliance Index Values of The Institutional Competence Scale

	Unrelated	Multi-Factor Model	Limit Values
χ^2 / sd	3,861	2,649	≤ 5
GFI	,867	,927	
CFI	,930	,965	$\geq 0,80$
NFI	,895	,932	
RMSEA	,098	,076	≤ 0.05

The fit index values found as a result of the confirmatory factor analysis conducted on the unrelated model were $\chi^2 / sd = 3.861$, GFI = 0.867, CFI = 0.930, NFI = 0.895, and RMSEA = 0.098. When the fit indices listed in Table 3 were compared with the cut-off values, it was concluded that the fit index did not have a good fit index. Considering the modification index values, it was concluded that the relationship between the error covariance values of Item 1 and Item 3, Item 5 and Item 6, and Item 8 and Item 9 should be taken into consideration. Consequently, it was revealed that "the item pairs were under the same latent variable and were meaningfully close to each other" (Büyüköztürk et al., 2004). After correlating the errors found between the items with the covariances, the model was tested with CFA (Figure 1).

Figure 1. CGP Scale

The fit index values resulting from the confirmatory factor analysis applied to the model in Figure 1 are $\chi^2 / sd = 2.649$, GFI = 0.927, CFI = 0.965, NFI = 0.932,

and RMSEA = 0.076. Consequently, when the goodness-of-fit values were examined after the CFA, it was concluded that the variables monitored for the single-factor structure and 9-item measurement model represented the latent variables to the required level.

Table 4. Fit Index Values of the JS Scale

	Unrelated	Multi-Factor Model	Limit Values
χ^2 / sd	3,671	2,489	≤ 5
GFI	,827	,882	
CFI	,900	,945	$\geq 0,80$
NFI	,851	,899	
RMSEA	,094	,070	≤ 0.05

The confirmatory factor analysis performed on the unrelated model yielded the following fit index values: $\chi^2 / sd = 3.671$, GFI = 0.827, CFI = 0.900, NFI = 0.851, and RMSEA = 0.094. It was concluded that the fit index values were not good according to the cut-off values shown in Table 4. Considering the modification index values, it was predicted that the relationship between the covariance values of Items 2 and 3, Items 10 and 11, Items 13 and 14, and Items 16 and 17 should be considered. Accordingly, it was revealed that "the item pairs were under the same latent variable and were meaningfully close to each other" (Büyüköztürk et al., 2004). After correlating the errors between the aforementioned items with the covariances, the resulting model was tested with CFA (Figure 2).

Figure 2. JS Scale

The fit index values found as a result of the confirmatory factor analysis performed on the model in Figure 2 are $\chi^2/df = 2.489$, GFI=0.882, CFI=0.945, NFI=0.899, RMSEA=0.070. When the goodness of fit values were examined after CFA, it was understood that the variables observed for the measurement model consisting of a 2-factor structure and 20 items also represented the latent variables at a sufficient level.

Table 5. Skewness and Kurtosis Values

Scale	N	Skewness	Kurtosis
Corporate Governance Principles	305	-,797	,214
Job Satisfaction	305	-,707	,762
Internal Satisfaction	305	-,692	,748
External Satisfaction	305	-,698	,498

As a result of the analysis, the variables showed normal distribution.

4. Findings

Descriptive Analysis Results for Variables

Table 6. Descriptive Analysis Results for Variables

Scale	N	Min.	Maks.	Ave.	SS
Corporate Governance Principles	305	9,00	45,00	31,71	8,89
Job Satisfaction	305	1,00	5,00	3,58	,82
Internal Satisfaction	305	1,00	5,00	3,60	,83
External Satisfaction	305	1,00	5,00	3,55	,85

The average of the answers given by the participants to the questions about the CGP scale was 31.71 ± 8.89 , the lowest score was 9.00, and the highest score was 45.00. In their answers to the questions about the JS scale, the average of the answers was 3.58 ± 0.82 , the lowest score was 1.00 and the highest score was 5.00. While the average of the answers given to the questions about the sub-dimensions of JS was 3.60 ± 0.83 , the lowest score was 1.00 and the highest score was 5.00; The average of the answers to the questions about ES was 3.55 ± 0.85 , the lowest score was 1.00, and the highest score was 5.00.

Pearson Correlation Analysis Results

Table 7. Pearson Correlation Analysis Results

	1.	2.	3.	4.	5.	6.	7.	8.
1. Corporate Governance Principles	r_p	,566	,542	,416	,549	,563	,511	,539
	p	,000	,000	,000	,000	,000	,000	,000
2. Job Satisfaction	r_p		1	,461	,649	,688	,968	,970
	p			,000	,000	,000	,000	,000
3. Internal Satisfaction	r_p						1	,879
	p							,000
4. External Satisfaction	r_p							1
	p							

When the Pearson Correlation test results in Table 7 are examined;

A positive and moderate correlation was found between Corporate Governance Principles and Job Satisfaction in the participants of the study ($p < 0.05$).

A positive and moderate correlation was found between Corporate Governance Principles and Internal and External Satisfaction in the participants of the study ($p < 0.05$).

Regression Analyzes

Table 8. Impact of Corporate Governance Principles on Job Satisfaction

	Non-standardized coefficients		Standardized coefficients			F	R ²
	B	Std. mistake	β	T	p		
Stationary	10,612	1,929		5,502	,000		
Job Satisfaction	5,897	,526	,542	11,219	,000	125,860	,293

Dependent variable: JS

* p<0.01

According to the results of the regression analyzes according to Table 8, the model is statistically significant and can explain 29.3% of the variance of JS of the CGP ($R^2=.293$; $F(1.3033)= 125,860$, $p<0.001$). According to the results, CGP predicted the variance of JS statistically significantly and positively ($\beta=0.542$, $t=11.219$, $p<0.001$). In short, the people participating in the study affect their JS levels positively. In addition, when the regression equation is considered and other predictive variables are kept constant, a one-unit increase in the CGP levels of the participants will provide a 5,897 increase in the JS level.

Table 9. The Effect of CGP on Internal and External Satisfaction

	Non-standardized coefficients		Standardized coefficients			F	R ²
	B	Std. hata	β	t	p		
Stationary	10,795	1,934		5,582	,000		
Internal Satisfaction	1,719	1,081	,161	1,590	,113	4,395	,297
External Satisfaction	4,146	1,054	,398	3,933	,000	4,395	

Dependent variables: Internal and External Satisfaction

* p<0.05

According to Table 9, it is determined that the model is statistically significant, but it disappears when the effect of the level of CGP on the ES of the participants is included in the IS. Looking at the regression analysis results in Table 9, CGP can define 29.7% of the variance of ES ($R^2=.297$; $F(2.302)= 63,696$, $p<0.005$). The results indicate that CGP positively and statistically significantly predict the variance level of ES ($\beta=0.398$, $t=3.933$, $p<0.005$). In short, the CGP positively affect the ES levels of the participants in the study. Furthermore, considering the regression equation and holding other predictor variables constant, a one-unit increase in participants' level of CGP will result in a 4.146 increase in ES.

5. Conclusion and Recommendation

In today's business world, we can say that human resources are an important resource for businesses to gain an advantage in the competitive environment and keep up with the times. For this reason, it is becoming more and more difficult for businesses to retain and find talented employees. Finding, attracting and retaining qualified employees is crucial to business success.

Organizations need to retain talented employees for long-term growth and guaranteed success. Influencing staff positively is a way to encourage people to do their best and to develop an environment and culture in which they want to stay. Success comes from the qualified people that the organizations have.

The main purpose of human resources and workforce management is to improve the employee's attitude towards work. JS is an important area of research for many years, and many researchers are investigating the relationship between JS and the factors affecting it.

Based on the research results, the following suggestions can be listed;

In today's business world, we can say that human resources are an important resource for businesses to gain an advantage in the competitive environment and keep up with the times. For this reason, it is becoming more and more difficult for businesses to retain and find talented employees. Finding, attracting and retaining qualified employees is crucial to business success. At this point, CGP are at the forefront of the issues that come to mind.

The quality of corporate governance affects trust, as businesses have access to capital for their growth and capital providers provide value on fair terms. A good position of CG not only gives partners and other shareholders the confidence to protect their rights, but also positively affects operating personnel.

JS is extremely important for employees to stay happy and present their level in the best possible way. Satisfied employees will remain highly committed to their organization, even in the worst conditions. The existence of the organization depends on the passion of the employees for their work, and passion only arises when the employees are satisfied with their work and the organization as a whole.

The effect of CGP on organizational attractiveness and JS should also be evaluated in terms of other sectors.

As a result, CGP positively affects the levels of Organizational Attractiveness and JS. JS is extremely important for employees to stay happy and present their level in the best possible way. Satisfied employees will remain highly committed to their organization, even in the worst conditions. The existence of the organization depends on the passion of the employees for their work, and passion only arises when the employees are satisfied with their work and the organization.

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